

Rules for Behavioral Coding

To assess participants' observable need for explanations during the experiment, we defined five behavioral categories that indicate a need for explanations. In all cases, the participant is confused about their failure at the task and seeks information, indicating a conflict between their flawed mental model and the system's actual behavior:

1. **The participant "re-opens" the tutorial video after encountering an intended error.**
→ This behavior indicates an explicit demand for explanations, according to Deters et al. [1].
2. **The participant opens the software manual after encountering an intended error.**
→ This behavior indicates an explicit demand for explanations, according to Deters et al. [1].
3. **The participant displays noteworthy behavior after encountering an intended error.**
→ This category summarizes the "behavior-based" user indicators, as defined by Deters et al. [2]. Examples are click-spamming, repetitive actions and back-and-forth navigation.
4. **The participant verbally asks for an explanation or help after encountering an intended error.**
→ This behavior indicated a need for explanations shown through "physical reactions", specifically "verbal expression", as defined by Deters et al. [2].
5. **The participant explicitly indicates a need for explanations in the post-experiment survey.**
→ This was an additional measure implemented to give participants an opportunity to state an explicit need for explanations. It is not based in specific literature.

[1] Deters, Hannah, et al. "Explanations on demand-a technique for eliciting the actual need for explanations." 2023 IEEE 31st International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW). IEEE, 2023.

[2] Deters, Hannah, et al. "Identifying Explanation Needs: Towards a Catalog of User-based Indicators." 2025 IEEE 33rd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE). IEEE, 2025.